

BASIC APPROACHES AND PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING TEXT STRUCTURE

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Abstract: This article discusses the approaches and principles of teaching text structure in native language lessons. Research works, methodological manuals, and scientific-methodological articles on the methodology of teaching the native language interpret approaches, principles, and patterns related to the study of language phenomena. Based on existing approaches and principles, the main approaches and principles have been identified for extracting theoretical information about text structure, determining ways to teach it, consolidating knowledge, developing skills, creating exercises for text creation and improvement, and defining types of work.

Keywords: text structure, approach, principle, textual errors, rule, oral and written speech, speech and linguistic competence, speech culture.

Introduction. Educational work related to text composition aims to provide knowledge on various components, form skills and abilities, and ultimately develop the ability to create texts, thus acquiring speech and linguistic competencies. The process of developing educational content, conditions, means, methods, and techniques that serve these purposes and meet today's requirements begins with defining the basic approaches and principles to be followed in this process.

Based on the research objective, the main approaches and principles were divided into three groups:

- 1) the main approaches and principles to be followed when extracting theoretical information about text structure and determining ways to teach it;
- 2) main approaches and principles applied in developing a system of exercises for consolidating knowledge and forming skills;
- 3) main approaches and principles applied in determining types of exercises and tasks for text creation, creative work, and its improvement.

Analysis and results. Below, we discuss the approaches and principles included in the first and second groups.

I. Among the main approaches and principles used in identifying theoretical information about text structure and determining ways to teach them, a differentiated approach to the components of theoretical information (definition, classification, description, rule) plays an important role. This is because, for students to be able to compose texts competently, it is necessary to teach them, first and foremost, the rules, and sometimes descriptions close to rules. The knowledge used in this process is built on the basis of learned terms and definitions. For example, pronominal connection of sentences refers to the stage when pronouns as a part of speech have been assimilated into the student's speech.

The principle of extracting and interpreting theoretical information about text structure from the textbook means using the knowledge gained in native language lessons to teach text structure as well. Below we focus on the information provided in the "Mother Tongue" textbook:

"In connecting a word to a word and a sentence to a sentence, not only the content but also the grammatical aspect is important. Auxiliary words that serve to connect more than one word or sentence are called conjunctions.

And; however; but; because; or; either..., or...; now..., now...; sometimes..., sometimes... are conjunctions.

Conjunctions are used to connect words or simple sentences.

The largest and hardest-working part of the human body is the liver (word-to-word connection).

The liver is the filter of the human body because it protects us from various harmful substances that enter our body (connecting two simple sentences) [1. P.61].

From this theoretical information, the following rule is derived:

Conjunctions such as "and," "but," "however," "because," "or," "either... or...," "now... now...," "sometimes... sometimes..." serve not only to connect words with words but also to connect sentences with sentences. For example: Doctors don't call the liver a filter of the human body for nothing. Because the liver constantly works to protect us from various harmful substances that enter our body [1. P. 62].

In this example, the conjunction "because" connects two sentences.

Recently, the practice of studying knowledge within a single topic by dividing it into modules has been established. For example, the division of concepts related to the interconnection of two sentences into modules, that is, a modular educational approach, is being introduced. For instance, the personal pronoun (it), demonstrative pronouns, defining pronouns, and other types of pronouns form separate modules, i.e., rules on individual topics are studied.

L.O. Denisova explains the modular learning technology as follows:

"Modular learning technology equips students with the practical experience of independent learning.

The teacher selects content for the topic in advance, divides it into modules, and targets the results to be achieved for each. The teacher specifies the topic, tasks, knowledge, skills, and abilities on the technological map.

1. Familiarization with the topics and tasks, assigning individual goals and objectives to each student.

2. Control.

3. Target program of actions, intermediate control, self-control and mutual control.

4. Additional material, assistance to a classmate, alternative learning activities.

5. Expert control, i.e., teacher supervision.

6. Assessment of the general and individual tasks and goals of each student's educational activity and correction of knowledge and skills in this regard.

7. Differentiated homework" [2. P. 8].

When studying the structure of the text, the principle of taking into account the possibilities that the educational content of the textbook provides for this work is manifested in the connection with the lesson materials.

As explained in the article by E.S. Antonova, "The essence of the linguistic approach to the analysis of speech works consists in determining the dependence of the text on the author's purpose, since the influence of the speaker's or writer's pragmatic instruction extends to the expression of the entire thought. When analyzing textbooks from this point of view, exercises based on individual words and sentences become useless. Individual language units make it difficult to determine the lexical and grammatical meaning" [3. P.12]. The author sees the reason for this in the detachment of the word and sentence from life.

"Within the framework of the cognitive approach, the text is considered as a product of a person's speech thinking activity, that is, it engages both the speaker/writer (the author) and the listener/reader (the addressee's mental premises) during the process of thinking (in the processes of analogy, analysis, conclusion, and interpretation of the text)" [3. P.12].

In works focused on speech culture, oral and written speech are integrated. Indeed, written speech regulates oral speech, and it is also constantly developing, demonstrating its influence on the "sharpening of the pencil" of students as they perform text composition exercises. Speech culture also develops in this manner.

To date, the types of textual errors that should be considered when determining the educational content for each component of text structure have been identified. The reasons for some of these errors have been explained by methodologist scholars based on a linguomethodological approach [4. P.157], [5. P.50-52].

The principle of taking into account knowledge acquired in primary grades also plays an important role in developing rules for text structure.

Another organizational and technical component of text is planning. Students also make some mistakes in this regard: they confuse the parts of the plan. The principle of relying on knowledge and skills acquired in primary grades plays an important role in determining and correcting the sequence of plan parts. Indeed, exercises for sequentially organizing plan items given in primary school "Native Language and Reading Literacy," as well as in high school "Native Language" textbooks, are recommended, which ultimately allows for achieving the expected result [6. P.19], [7. P.53].

Write the headings in the correct sequence according to the paragraphs of the text.

Smart
decision

Intelligent
child

The incident
of the night

Migration

Arrange the given sentences in such an order that they can serve as an outline for the audio text you have listened to.

Hasan ibn al-Haysam is the father of optics
The scientist's views on the eye and its structure
Ancient people's ideas about vision and light
The experience of Hasan ibn al-Haysam

The principle of interdependence between language levels and the development of oral and written speech plays an important role in the educational content of text structure.

When determining the content of text-related learning, didactic principles such as progressing from simple to complex, from easy to difficult, and from specific to general are also applied.

The principle of systematicity and sequential stages indicates the need to plan and study the concepts of text structure as an integrated system. This principle applies not only to the content of education but also to educational activities.

The principle of considering the latest achievements in linguistics is one of the fundamental principles for teaching students text composition.

The principle of consistency plays a crucial role in studying text structure. According to this principle, each component should be interconnected with other components, consistently distributed, and studied progressively over the years. For example, the use of a pronoun instead of a noun in the text is presented as replacing a noun in the nominative case with a pronoun in the nominative case. Later, students practice using pronouns in accusative, dative, locative, or ablative cases in subsequent sentences instead of nouns in the first sentence. Finally, such substitutions are observed within the framework of textual synonyms. This consistent increase in complexity of the linguistic phenomenon allows for studying it with a uniform level of effort. [8. P. 68].

When formulating rules, according to the principle of adapting to the student's level, theoretical knowledge about text structure and practical skills should be provided in content and volume that students can handle.

In addition to considering students' age characteristics, mental capabilities, and level of speech development, the following principles are also observed:

- the principle of accounting for knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired in the native language;
- the principle of relying on students' experience in analyzing linguistic phenomena;
- the principle of relying on language intuition;
- the principle of developing students' thinking, logical reasoning, and creative abilities;
- the principle of comprehensibility;
- the principle of considering students' interests.
- "the principle of psychological comfort" [9. P.12].

Furthermore, the teacher must determine the level of children's oral speech and consider ways to build upon these skills.

Experts say the following about the need for students to set goals: "A brief conversation about the topic and purpose of the previous lesson creates a situation for goal setting. Students must certainly define their own goals - without this, the work of the brain (the underlying meaning, the thought to be pondered) does not emerge and the speech readiness that activates inner speech does not arise. Due to the formulated thought, the evaluation of the addressee and the selection of linguistic means for external speech - the text - begins. The reaction to the author's speech - whether expected or unexpected - encourages the refinement of the statement of thought (text) " [3. P.13].

II. Basic Approaches and Principles Followed in Developing a System of Exercises for Consolidating Knowledge and Forming Skills

The principle of relying on students' experience in analyzing linguistic phenomena plays an important role in transitioning to the analysis of textual structure features. In particular, analyses based on rules prove to be appropriate.

To fully realize the educational process in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities related to teaching text structure, it is necessary to ensure students' literacy. Literacy is achieved by eliminating textual errors, mastering the rules of text structure, and applying them in practice. From this perspective, the principle of addressing textual errors should take a leading role in the process of teaching students text structure.

Various logical, semantic, and grammatical errors are found in texts composed by students.

In the textbook "Methods of Teaching Russian in Primary Grades," logical and compositional errors are divided into 5 groups:

- 1) repetition of facts, events, etc.;
- 2) omission of an important sentence;
- 3) disruption of cause-effect relationships;
- 4) disruption of chronological sequence;

5) placing inconsistent items in a row (For example, a child, while narrating a summer incident, focuses on what they did during the day. It's incorrect to speak of summer and daytime consecutively in the same context).

Compositional errors are added to logical errors:

- poorly structured introduction or conclusion, or the complete absence of these parts;
- excessive length or brevity (or abruptness, omission of an important sentence) in parts of the essay;

- deviation from the topic (such deviations distract the reader);
- insufficient supporting elements, references, and evidence in reasoning;
- unjustified deviation from the plan.

Logical errors arise due to violations of the laws of logic: the law of identity, the law of non-contradiction, the law of excluded middle, and the law of sufficient reason.

The reason for compositional and content errors is the inability to consolidate thoughts. For instance, errors related to the use of factual information; errors in incorporating descriptive elements into narrative text; errors in formulating conclusions; errors related to text types (descriptive text, narrative text, argumentative text).

"The disruption of word connections in lengthy sentences is explained by the fact that students still have a limited capacity for 'regulatory synthesis' of text, that is, the ability to synthesize text based on progression in the brain (operative memory mechanism): in a 10-year-old student, this capacity does not exceed 5-7 words. Consequently, they begin writing without knowing how they will end the sentence" [10. P.13].

Constructive errors (such as incorporating hadiths, proverbs, wise sayings, etc. into sentences) are frequently found in texts composed by students. These errors sometimes involve slightly altering proverbs, hadiths, or wise sayings and presenting them as their own words, incorrect use of punctuation marks, and unnecessary repetitions. Particularly, presenting these sentences as reported speech requires mastery of knowledge and skills related to punctuation marks.

In texts composed by 5th-grade students, errors related to paragraph indentation, sentence boundaries, and incorrect use of punctuation marks are common. While errors in paragraph indentation and sentence boundaries can be quickly corrected after learning the rules and completing 3-4 exercises, it is not possible to learn and master all situations at once regarding the use of punctuation marks in various sentences due to their diverse applications.

"Based on students' personal participation in education, the following principles can be identified:

- principle of independence;
- principle of active engagement;
- principle of striving for cooperation.
- principle of future orientation [8. P. 63-64].

Considering students' age characteristics, mental capabilities, and level of speech development, we distinguish the following principles from those identified:

- the principle of taking into account knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired in the native language;
- the principle of considering children's age and personal characteristics;
- the principle of relying on students' experience in analyzing linguistic phenomena;
- the principle of relying on language intuition;
- the principle of developing their thinking, logical reasoning, and creative abilities [8. P.67].

O.O. Kharchenko emphasizes the need to apply the competency-based approach based on the following types of competence: linguistic competence, speech competence, communicative competence, and language (grammatical) competence [10. P.37].

In the "National Curriculum for the Native Language," "Speech Competencies" are expressed through requirements for types of speech activity (oral speech skills, written speech skills, comprehension skills, listening comprehension). "Linguistic competence," as defined in speech competencies, is also specified in the form of requirements for four types of speech activity. Speech competencies reflect requirements more closely related to the communicative aspects of speech. In linguistic competencies, the requirements are expressed using phrases like "to be able to explain" and "to be able to apply." These requirements are realized in terms of understanding language units and the ability to use them in speech. Both competencies are connected with speech activity. However, it is difficult to acquire linguistic competence without studying the components related to text structure: text composition skills can only be acquired through extensive practice using practical methods. One of the most important tasks of native language lessons is to provide prompt assistance to students.

When creating a text, it is advisable for students to pay attention to its expressiveness and content, use artistic devices and emotional-expressive language units, and demonstrate cultural qualities as the author of the text.

As I.Yu.Gats notes: "The educational role of work on speech culture is very significant. Essentially, its content aims to foster in children a respectful attitude towards their native language, a sense of pride in their people's cultural traditions, and a sense of responsibility for preserving them. Such a requirement necessitates an informal, flexible approach that awakens students' interest in the object and subject of linguistic research during the lesson. The teacher must carefully select and consider language facts, offering students vivid texts that are also accessible to their perception" [11. P.7]. There is no doubt that such texts recommended for analysis will ultimately encourage students to compose similar texts. Naturally, throughout life, a person is concerned about their oral speech and strives to master speech culture. These efforts initially arise in oral form: while listening to people who speak beautifully and pleasantly, as well as orators, the student internalizes and adopts models for

developing their own speech. In these processes, the principle of unity between education and upbringing is observed.

Conclusion. One of the most important and serious principles is taking into account the textual errors that students make in exercises requiring analysis of a text structure component or composing a text using that component.

According to R.Yuldashev and M.Rikhsiyeva, "Starting to express an idea and ending it in a way that is difficult to understand leads not only to issues with individual sentence content, but also to incompleteness of the whole text's content and ambiguity of the intended idea. It would be correct to consider such shortcomings as textual errors. They can be classified as follows:

1) mixing subtopics covered in the text, inability to distinguish paragraph boundaries in relation to them;

2) disruption of logic in thought expression;

3) textual errors in consistent presentation of thought in descriptive texts;

4) textual errors in consistent presentation of thought in narrative texts;

5) textual errors in consistent presentation of thought in argumentative texts;

6) textual errors characterized by awkwardness in sentence content;

7) lexical errors leading to ambiguity of thought" [4. P.58].

When recommending exercises designed to teach students text creation, it is advisable to consider both the textual and non-textual errors they tend to make.

Mastering text composition rules means acquiring competence ranging from sentence construction to creating official documents or literary works. Therefore, the entire educational process involves developing relevant competencies in students, which means approaching educational content and methods based on a competency-based approach.

Linguistic phenomena, manifesting through connected speech, demonstrate their real communicative nature. As long as linguistic rules are not studied through text structure, the acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities will remain at the level of forming linguistic competence. For this reason, educational materials on text structure should be incorporated into native language education content based on systematically defined approaches and principles.

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